

Polymeric Based Pellets as Intelligent Drug Delivery Systems

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ABSTRACT

The small intestine is where most conventional oral formulations are mostly absorbed. This restricts their usage in the treatment of several colon disorders since the medicine must act topically at the site of inflammation. This opened the door for the development of an intelligent colonic drug delivery system, which enhanced therapeutic effectiveness, decreased dosing frequency and potential side effects, and increased patient acceptance—particularly in situations where enemas or other topical preparations might not be sufficient to treat inflammation alone. This study's primary goal was to develop a smart medication delivery system based on pH-sensitive polymeric formulations made using a free-radical bulk polymerization technique. In the formulations, 5-amino salicylic acid was used as a model drug and Capmul MCM C8 was added to increase bioavailability. The in vitro swelling and release evaluation showed that the developed system may be able to delay drug release under conditions that mimic the stomach and small intestine while triggering it under conditions that mimic the colon, indicating its potential usefulness as a smart colonic drug delivery system.

Key Words: Mesalamine; Intelligent Delivery; Sustainable Development; Smart Polymers; Colon Disorders.

References

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